

CRIMINOLOGY IN ACTION - 2025

Title: Fraud: a Hydra emergent in new forms in the Maltese Islands

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BACKGROUND

Malta is not immune from fraudulent activities. In fact, it is one of the highest reported crimes in the Annual CrimeMalta Observatory league of tables. One can only understand the dynamics of the crime of Fraud from a tripartite perspective: the fact (report), the victimisation aspect (real and virtual victims) as well as the criminological perspective (the what, why, when, where, who and how).

What makes fraud uniquely interesting in the study of crime revolves around its new internationalised reach as against the pre-internet period when fraud was mainly committed in bounded domains, where fraudsters lived and operated. The internet expanded this drastically, such that the medium became the main conveyor for international offenders to predate on hapless victims irrespective of location, language, gender, age, level of education, wealth and status. The cases of Shwe-Kokko and Lay Kay Kaw (Strangio, 203) give rise to the understanding that offenders are organised in a factory-style organisation, enslave persons to serve as fraudsters, operate in a legal limbo and transact monies that are difficult if not impossible to trace. An interesting media take on the structures called “The Beekeeper” (imdb.com, 2024) focusing on the victimisation emanating from such crimes by a factory run by the son of a politician, ironically reflects a real-life occurrence where a former Malaysian deputy minister was arrested over a cyber scam park in 2024 (Justice For Myanmar, 2024)

This background research paper presents the research process and findings emanating from the study of fraud, which was eventually presented as a keynote speech in June 2025 during the Malta Bankers’ Association Fraud conference held on 12th June 2025.

In this paper, any reference to Malta, relates to all the Maltese Islands.

LEGAL FRAMEWORK AND THE ELEMENTS OF FRAUD

Under Maltese criminal law, fraud is delineated in Chapter 9, Title IX, Sub-Title III of the Criminal Code, encompassing Articles 293 through 310C (Legislazzjoni.mt, 2025).

Fraud is established through four critical elements: a deceptive act or misrepresentation, intent to cause unlawful gain or injury, a direct causal link between the act and its outcome, and the presence of *mens rea*, or guilty mind, indicating deliberate intent to deceive. These elements distinguish fraud from acts of mere negligence.

For a fraudulent act to be established, four elements must be satisfied:

- **Deceptive Act or Misrepresentation:** This includes false representation, concealment of material facts, document forgery, or misleading conduct.
- **Unlawful Intent:** The perpetrator must aim to achieve unlawful gain or inflict injury—financial or otherwise.
- **Mens Rea:** The act must be committed with knowledge and intent, distinguishing it from mere negligence.
- **Actus Reus - Causality:** A direct link must exist between the deception and the resulting harm or benefit.

Under Maltese Law, penalties are contingent upon the severity of the act and may include imprisonment, fines (*multa*), and restitution. Aggravating circumstances—such as breach of public trust, targeting vulnerable populations, or links to organised crime—warrant enhanced sentencing.

Fraud is punishable under the general scale of penalties outlined in the Maltese Criminal Code (Articles 7–32). Depending on the severity, legal consequences may include imprisonment (with longer sentences for aggravated cases), fines (*multa*), and restitution to victims as determined by the courts.

Aggravating circumstances increase the seriousness of the offence and the penalties imposed. These include fraud committed by public officers or professionals in breach of trust, acts that involve large-scale financial harm or target vulnerable individuals and offenses linked to organised criminal activity.

CRIMINOLOGICAL SHIFT: FROM OUTDOORS TO INDOORS

Traditional crimes have increasingly moved into the digital realm. Fraud exemplifies this shift, evolving beyond national boundaries and exploiting systemic vulnerabilities. As a crime type, it transcends social strata, making every individual and institution a potential target.

This shift is detailed in the CrimeMalta Observatory 2024 Annual Crime Report with data originally sourced from the Malta Police National Police System (NPS):

“It is vital to note that the shift in locational structure that became starkly evident in 2023 where crime has moved indoors, is still high at 34% of all crimes. These categories of crimes are potentially out of reach of proactive visual capture through deterrence by community police, mobile units and technologies. Crimes have shifted from the physical outdoor urban construct to an indoor real and virtual construct, where the victim is targeted in their ‘safe havens’, oftentimes playing a role in the same offence, particularly online fraud. Policing and its effectiveness used to cater for 96% of all crimes within an outdoor setting as at 2004. As virtual and digital realities started shaking the societal norms, in conjunction with new realities such as changes in legislation (domestic violence, money laundering, amongst others), the physical incident component shifted gradually from the outdoors scenario to the indoors one. With 39% of crimes occurring indoors in 2023 and 35% in 2024, within the safety of one’s home, out of reach of security services, a need for individual awareness has never been more critical: from 4% ‘indoor’ crime in 2004, such jumped to 13% in 2014 and 35% in 2024. Inversely, policing experiences with outdoor crime has reached a stage where from 96% in 2004, this shifted to 87% in 2013 and dropping to 65% in 2024. Policing’s proactivity is effective but the indoors scenario posits entirely different challenges: it is the individual’s foresight of potential victimisation and their eventual action that takes the fore. The need for awareness of potential victimisation within one’s abode has reached a state that requires extensive campaigns and awareness-raising activities remains critical.” (Formosa et al, 2025)

AN INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

Fraud reports constitute a significant change and varies based on crime sprees and also on the level of awareness and buttressing from institutions and victims.

The number of fraudulent gains reported is staggering, particularly since victims realise their error too late to affect recouping of funds, particularly due to the international limits that dictate when international organisations where Europol or Interpol can be involved. There are also time limits where a bank can affect a transaction, prior to blocking a payment, often resulting in too late an action as the victim might realise considerable hours or days following the actual transaction.

The European Banking Authority and European Central Bank in its 2024 report on payment fraud, published its findings on the absolute and relative levels of payment fraud in volume terms (H1 2023), which identified that Malta, in comparison to the EU/EEA levels, experienced higher rates of incidents in the Credit Transfers and Cards (issuer) categories, lower rates in the Cash Withdrawals and E-money categories and no incidents in the Direct Debits category as depicted in Figure 1 (European Banking Authority and European Central Bank, 2024).

Europol and INTERPOL both play critical roles in supporting the investigation and prevention of transnational fraud, particularly when cases involve organised criminal networks or cross-border financial transactions. INTERPOL assists when fraud spans multiple countries, offering and coordination via its National Central Bureaus, as detailed on its Financial Crime page (Interpol, 2025). Europol, through the European Financial and Economic Crime Centre (EFECC) (Europol, 2025a), intervenes in cases affecting two or more EU Member States, providing intelligence support, operational coordination, and secure information exchange via its SIENA application (Europol, 2025b). Both agencies respond to requests from national authorities and focus on major fraud types including VAT carousel fraud, investment scams, cyber-enabled fraud, and schemes linked to money laundering or terrorism financing.

Figure 1: EBA and ECB Report on Payment Fraud Detail

Table 2: Absolute and relative levels of payment fraud in volume terms (H1 2023)

Country	Credit transfers		Direct debits		Cards (issuer)		Cash withdrawals		E-money	
	Volume of fraudulent transactions	Fraud in % of total payments	Volume of fraudulent transactions	Fraud in % of total payments	Volume of fraudulent transactions	Fraud in % of total payments	Volume of fraudulent transactions	Fraud in % of total payments	Volume of fraudulent transactions	Fraud in % of total payments
AT	12 620	0.003%	55	0.000%	63 620	0.008%	567	0.001%	82	0.003%
CY	141	0.001%	269	0.004%	7 822	0.009%	59	0.001%	873	0.021%
MT	587	0.007%	0	0.000%	8 247	0.017%	46	0.001%	1 144	0.005%
NL	275 786	0.014%	1 238 110	0.109%	377 663	0.012%	25 439	0.029%	112	0.001%
EU/EEA	616 479	0.003%	1 496 599	0.014%	7 306 767	0.015%	173 639	0.005%	541 432	0.012%

Source: amended from the European Banking Authority and European Central Bank, 2024, Pg 32

THE MALTESE SCENARIO

The CrimeMalta Observatory reported that in 2024:

“At the third ranking, Fraud experienced 2,394 cases, specifically pushed by fraudulent gains through mobile, messaging and online payment scams impersonating service, delivery and ancillary services. Down from the record 2,905 cases registered in 2023, the figure is also lower than the 2376 cases registered in 2021. The Fraud category registered 14.4% of all crimes reported in 2024, up from 160 cases in 2004 and 430 in 2014.” (Formosa et al, 2025)

The report also notes that:

“Fraud has experienced a decrease of 511 cases (18%). The cases reached 2,394 cases in 2024 (14.4% of all crimes), down from 2,905 cases in 2023.

- 2004-2024: Increase of 1,396% from 160 cases in 2004 to 2,394 in 2024
- 2014-2024: Increase of 364% from 430 cases in 2014 to 2,394 in 2024

These significant changes in reporting can be attested by the reports made to the Malta Police Force between 2008 and 2024, where from 245 cases (or 2% of all incidents reported in 2008, these went up to 2,394 cases in 2024 (14% of all incidents) (Figures 2 and 3). The highest peak was experienced in 2023 at 2,905 cases constituting 17% of all offences reported in that year.

From 5th category in the Malta league of crime tables in 2024, Fraud was placed 5th between 2008 and 2015, joint 4th and 5th between 2017 and 2020, 3rd in 2021, 4th in 2022 and 3rd between 2023 and 2024.

The Fraud Crime category is further split into 12 sub-categories, comprising commercial, counterfeit, customs ordinance, exchange control, financial institution act, fraudulent gains, income tax, insurance, intellectual property rights, misappropriation, usury and vat.

Figure 4 and Table 1 depict the sub-categories of Fraud committed between 2008 and 2024, where the main component relates to fraudulent gains (14,599 cases or 87% of all fraud cases between 2008 and 2024 peaking at 2,814 cases or 97% in 2023 with a slightly lower 2,284 cases or 95% in 2024. Fraudulent gains are followed by misappropriation, commercial and counterfeit sub-categories (Table 1).

Figure 2: Reported Crime Counts and Percentages – Main 5 categories (2008 – 2024)

	5 th										4 ^{th-5th}		3 rd	4 th	3 rd			
	Reported Crime Percentages - Main 5 Categories (2008 - 2024)																	
	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Grand Total
THEFT	59	57	58	60	56	48	49	50	51	48	41	43	35	28	31	28	31	48
DAMAGE	17	15	14	12	17	26	25	24	23	22	25	25	24	22	24	20	18	21
FRAUD	2	2	2	2	2	4	3	3	3	5	6	5	6	15	10	17	14	5
DOMESTIC VIOLENCE	3	5	5	6	7	6	6	7	7	7	8	9	13	11	12	12	13	7
BODILY HARM	7	8	8	8	7	5	6	5	5	5	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	6
ALL OTHER CRIMES	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

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	Reported Crime Counts - Main 5 Categories (2008 - 2024)																	
	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Grand Total
THEFT	8,127	6,843	7,774	8,522	8,690	8,469	8,199	8,654	8,822	8,255	6,528	6,631	4,578	4,612	4,731	5,218	161,142	
DAMAGE	2,316	1,796	1,937	1,765	2,613	4,658	4,107	4,129	4,017	3,832	3,933	3,939	3,203	3,512	3,558	3,336	3,062	68,961
FRAUD	245	283	234	269	359	626	430	470	500	787	1,032	821	811	2,376	1,562	2,905	2,394	16,748
DOMESTIC VIOLENCE	450	543	660	849	1,028	1,024	1,048	1,205	1,272	1,257	1,341	1,326	1,645	1,741	1,830	2,071	2,225	21,631
BODILY HARM	1,006	955	1,043	1,108	1,032	958	990	926	901	879	892	925	777	742	847	946	978	20,324
ALL OTHER CRIMES	1,660	1,534	1,717	1,776	1,900	1,863	1,879	1,754	1,786	2,126	2,199	1,947	2,073	2,936	2,524	2,866	2,785	43,542
GRAND TOTAL	13,804	11,954	13,365	14,289	15,622	17,598	16,653	17,138	17,298	17,136	15,925	15,589	13,087	15,785	14,933	16,855	16,662	332,348

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Figure 3: Reported Crime Types in Malta (2008 – 2024) – Percentage of Total

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Figure 4: Fraud Reports by Sub-Category in Malta (2008 – 2024) – Counts

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Table 1: Fraud Reports by Sub-Category in Malta (2008 – 2024) – Counts

Main and Sub-Categories	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Grand Total
FRAUD	245	283	234	269	359	626	430	470	500	787	1032	821	811	2376	1562	2905	2394	16748
FRAUDULENT GAINS	211	239	201	218	298	495	344	354	405	675	901	698	709	2269	1449	2814	2284	14599
MISAPPROPRIATION	9	15	10	15	14	75	36	52	42	56	65	60	59	69	71	67	79	799
COMMERCIAL	10	16	9	13	8	19	19	16	10	23	26	33	27	16	19	10	6	290
COUNTERFEIT	5	9	14	19	28	29	22	31	20	5	19	5	1	7	1	3	10	231
CUSTOMS ORDINANCE	6			2	5	4	2	7	12	14	13	9	5	6	5	5	4	99
USURY				1	3	2	6	7	3	4	2	4	4	3	10	3	2	54
INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS	3	2			1	2		1	2	3	3	2	2	3	2	1	5	32
EXCHANGE CONTROL									4	1	9	2	1	1				18
FINANCIAL INSTITUTION ACT					1			1	4	3		1		1		2	2	15
INCOME TAX	1	2							2				2	1	1		2	11
INSURANCE				1			1				2							6
VAT					1			1							3			5

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

VICTIMS OF FRAUD: OF GENDER, AGE, NATIONALITY AND LOCATION

Fraud posits a veritable diversity of victims, unbounded by age, gender, location, nationality or profession. In addition, it depicts its unrestricted modus operandi that spans time and space due to its increasingly virtual and international construct.

Victims of fraud have increased from 2% of all offences in 2008 to 14% in 2024 with a peak of 17% in 2023. The study identified that victims varies from the reported number of crimes since a crime may comprise multiple victims or in some cases where the victim is unknown but a case was reported. All cases are reported irrespective whether they occur in the real world or in cyber virtuality. As a case in focus in 2008 there were 232 victims for 245 cases, whilst in 2023 there were 2,918 victims for 2,905 cases and 2,283 victims for 2,284 cases in 2024 (Figure 5 and Table 2). Figure 6 depicts the victims of fraud by sub-category, again reflecting the fraudulent gains dominance.

In terms of **Gender**, victims comprise 59% male and 41% female (Figure 7), with **Age** comprising 3% under 18 years, 80% aged between 20 and 59, whilst the over 60 pl's category comprise 17% of all victims (Figure 8).

In terms of victims of fraud by **nationality**, the Maltese component comprised 80% with foreigners amounting to 15% and 5% did not identify nationality (Figure 9).

In terms of **Time** that victims report that they experienced this type of offence, the data depicts a peak at midnight then drastically dropping till 08:00 when the figures gradually increase to reach a major peak at 12:00, dropping again to a relatively stable counts from 13:00 to 17:00, then gradually diminishing till 23:00 (Figure 10). Note that this pattern relates to the hours of activity that the victim operates within and such an output requires further study to understand the difference between when the real time occurs and when the victims realise the incident and when they report such to the Police.

Figure 11 depicts the **Localities** where most reports are affected, which figures relate directly to the nearest location where reports could be made. The higher grossing localities are Birkirkara, followed by San Pawl il-Bahar, Sliema, Mosta and San Giljan.

Figure 5 and Table 2: Victims of Fraud as a Percentage of All Crimes in Malta (2008-2024)

Year	All Crimes	Fraud	% of All Crimes
2008	13,052	232	1.8
2009	11,762	281	2.4
2010	13,641	234	1.7
2011	14,514	255	1.8
2012	16,128	352	2.2
2013	18,053	831	4.6
2014	16,946	442	2.6
2015	17,352	464	2.7
2016	17,780	475	2.7
2017	17,684	774	4.4
2018	16,449	1,073	6.5
2019	26,866	803	3.0
2020	13,018	764	5.9
2021	14,968	2,296	15.3
2022	14,568	1,558	10.7
2023	16,865	2,918	17.3
2024	16,140	2,283	14.1
Grand Total	275,786	16,035	5.8

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Figure 6: Victims of Fraud by Sub-Category in Malta (2008-2024)

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Figure 7: Victims of Fraud by Gender in Malta (2008-2024)

Figure 8: Victims of Fraud by Age in Malta (2008-2024)

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Figure 9: Victims of Fraud by Nationality in Malta (2008-2024)

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Figure 10: Victims of Fraud by Time of Day in Malta (2008-2024)

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

Figure 11: Victims of Fraud by the Top 20 Localities in Malta (2008-2024)

Source: CrimeMalta Observatory, 2025

CONCLUSION

Whilst fraud is ever emergent through its inherent cross-border and virtual environments functionality, it is imperative that the societal foundations play their part in both understanding, mitigating and bringing to the fore new constructs to combat these new forms of crime. The PREFET structures come into play through their impact on the physical, natural, social and technological environments. Politics, Religion, Education, Family, Economic and Technological domains have formed societies over time with some losing the imperative in new forms of crime as such evolve, whilst others are resurgent, as are the Economic and Technological elements in the case of Fraud, however Politics has the imperative to legislate and affect change as are they ensure that the Legislative, Executive and Judicial arms of the powers of state are strengthened against the internationalisation of crime through proactive strategies.

The action imperative posits the need to revisit the DIKA methodology as it ensures that Fraud is understood through the Data-Information-Knowledge-Action functionality as a tool to combat fraud within the real and virtual worlds.

In conclusion, awareness is critical to ensure potential victims are forewarned of both the realities of their actions as well as the consequences of such. It must be noted that in terms of online fraud, victims unknowingly comprise an integral component of the offender-victim dynamic that where they partake to the actual approval of the crime through accepting an sms, message, email or other communications transaction.

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